

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

D2.3 R&I Secondment and Activity Reports on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
Project Title	<i>Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development</i>
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Deliverable Reference Number	D2.3
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Author(s)	Benjamin Stewart, Wulf Reiners
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R&I Secondment and Activity Reports on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

Seconded staff produce a report on each secondment to document R&I activities and achievements. Secondments and their accompanying deliverables take place within Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society or Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. At the onset of the secondment, in the Researcher Declaration Form, researchers indicate whether their research topic falls within WP2 or WP3.

The “R&I Secondment and Activity Reports” concept is fulfilled by each researcher in each individual secondment in a comprehensive “Secondment Activity Report”. The Secondment Activity Report includes,

- a) biographical and secondment details
- b) a summary of the research being performed
- c) proof of flights to and from the host country
- d) proof of housing in the host country
- e) information about the publication to be produced from the secondment

- f) information about the Digital Knowledge Product (DKP) to be produced from the secondment
- g) information about the presentation at the host institute
- h) a chronicle of research activities of the secondment
- i) confirmation of hours worked per month
- j) signature from the host institute, confirming the veracity of the Secondment Activity Report.

This deliverables is categorized as “public”. Therefore, in order to protect sensitive information in the Secondment Activity Reports, such as names of interview subjects and institutes, the following appendixes provide only the cover page (biographical information and research summary) of each secondment. On the cover page of each Secondment Activity Report, the birthdate of the secondee has been blackened out for reasons of data privacy and protection. The full reports are stored with the project coordinator in line with the Data Management Plan.

PRODIGEES implemented 74 research secondments for a total of 149 person-months (PM), including 56 individual staff members from the ten partner institutes. 54 secondments (108 PM) were performed for Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society. 20 secondments (41 PM) were performed for Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. Of the 74 secondments, 46% were performed by women and 54% were performed by Early Stage Researchers (ESRs). Whereas 60% of the PM were fulfilled by European-based researchers, researchers from non-European partners implemented 40% of the total 149 PM.

The following Secondment Activity Reports document research activity for secondments in WP2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society.

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Mr.
First Name	Andrew
Last Name	Deneault
Gender	M
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Canada
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	12-Jan-2024
End date of secondment	17-Apr-2024
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	FGV Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Email address	andrew.deneault@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	<p>Strengthening non-state transnational action (cities, companies, organizations collaborating across borders) for climate and biodiversity in the Global South</p> <p>Enhancing the online/ digital tracking of transnational initiatives in Brazil and worldwide.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Mr
First Name	Rifqi
Last Name	Rachman
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	
Nationality	Indonesia
Status – ESR or ER?	ESR
Start date of secondment	December 3 rd , 2024
End date of secondment	February 28 th , 2025
Originating institution	CSIS Indonesia
Host institute	IDOS
Email address	rifqi@saferinternetlab.org

<p>Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)</p>	<p>I successfully connected with the Bundesarchiv and interviewed four experts from the Stasi and the IT department. I also went to two Bundesarchiv offices: the Koblenz HQ and the Berlin Stasi department. I discussed with two experts in Koblenz and one expert in the Berlin-Lichtenberg office.</p> <p>On the other hand, I intend to visit the ANRI office in Jakarta to complement the interviews I conducted with three archivists when I was in Bonn.</p>
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Flight boarding pass (start of secondment) 2024.12.03- Arrived in Bonn, boarding pass attached below

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Anita
Last Name	Breuer
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Swiss / German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	29 January 2025
End date of secondment	1 March 2025
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Jakarta
Email address	Anita.breuer@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	During my stay in Jakarta, I conducted field research on the topic " Information integrity versus information pollution: Root causes and impacts on polarization, conflict and democratic quality in Indonesia." I applied an analytical framework developed by UNDP to study information pollution. According to this framework, four contexts are considered particularly relevant: 1) political
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	<p>landscape, 2) media landscape, 3) social landscape, 4) legislative and institutional landscape. In order to learn more about the drivers and impacts of information pollution in these four contexts, during my stay I conducted semi-structured interviews with xx experts. Experts included the following types of actors: media professionals, civil servants, academics (scholars of sociology as well as political and communication science), members of civil society organizations, staff of tech companies and practitioners in international development cooperation. Furthermore, during my stay, in coordination with Medelina Hendytio (Deputy Executive Director of CSIS), I organized and conducted a hybrid event entitled “<i>Towards Information Integrity: A Holistic Framework for Understanding Disinformation and Polarization Across Different Country Contexts</i>” that served both as additional instrument of data collection as well as an opportunity for academic exchanges.. The event, which was held on xxx, was streamed live xxx and is available there as a digital knowledge product.</p> <p>The work still to be done includes the transcription of the audio recordings of the interviews I conducted, as well as their systematic analysis. On this basis, I will prepare a publication in the IDOS Discussion Paper series - , envisaged publication end of 2025.</p> <p>Furthermore, in cooperation with IDOS communication department (Sabrina Heuwinkel) I am currently working on the production of another digital knowledge product on the topic of “Safeguarding Information Integrity. Good practices from Indonesia” in which I will present video statements which I collected from representatives of several Indonesian digital initiatives during my research stay.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Amit
Last Name	Kumar
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Indian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	28-07-2022
End date of secondment	25.09.2022
Originating institution	RIS, New Delhi, India
Host institute	IDOS, Bonn, Germany
Email address	amit.kumar@ris.org.in

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	The research work intended to provide an overview and analysis of the digital strategies and policies in the Europe and India towards promoting digitalisation for inclusive and sustainable development.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Carlos
Last Name	Domínguez
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	MEXICAN
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Experienced researcher
Start date of secondment	October 19 th 2021
End date of secondment	December 19 th 2021
Originating institution	Instituto Mora
Host institute	University of Hamburg
Email address	alcarlosv@gmail.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	I used the time to conduct interviews, undertake literature review on digitalisation and inequalities, as well as art, culture, and sustainable development. My secondment was also helpful to build a more concrete case study for future research.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Assessing the impact of open-source AI technology: Evidence from the Indian pharmaceutical industry
First Name	Michele
Last Name	Federle
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	Italian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	17/12/2023
End date of secondment	15/01/2024
Originating institution	LUISS Guido Carli [Rome]
Host institute	RIS [New Delhi]
Email address	mfederle@luiss.it

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	I tried to understand how the publication of AlphaFold (July 2021), an AI algorithm developed by Google DeepMind that sizably shortens the drug discovery process, affects the Indian pharmaceutical industry in terms of innovation capability. I mostly focused on building a solid identification strategy, working along
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	<p>two main lines of research: (i) mapping data sets to run a difference-in-differences specification to see whether and which pharmaceutical firms become more innovative after the innovation shock: (ii) reaching out to representatives of Indian business associations to create ties for collaboration.</p> <p>Outstanding work includes further videocall meetings with business association representatives, academics and business leaders (some of which are already scheduled), as well as follow-ups with earlier contacts.</p> <p>Some business associations showed interests in collaboration with the goal of running an experiment (informational treatment), whereby pharmaceutical firms are informed about the AlphaFold technology and workforce upskilling programs funded by the Indian government.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Laura
Last Name	Donath
Gender	female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	11.02.2023
End date of secondment	15.04.2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	FGV
Email address	donath.laura.ld@gmail.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	<p>Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different</p>
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	<p>administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p> <p>Although we did end our final report with an extensive conclusion, we have not yet developed explicit recommendations, which will be taken up by my colleagues, who will stay at IDOS to work on the publication of our report. The subsequent publication of our results thus also depicts a future work package.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Wulf
Last Name	Reiners
Gender	m
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	14 April 2022
End date of secondment	13 May 2022
Originating institution	German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE)
Host institute	Instituto Mora
Email address	wulf.reiners@die-gdi.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	The secondment to Instituto Mora had two objectives. First, it served the purpose to analyse and discuss Mexican and EU framings / narratives of digitalisation in view of their compatibility with sustainable development. The research culminated in a joint workshop at the hosting institution in collaboration with the Digital Transformation Centre DTC Mexico of the GIZ. Second, focus was put on the role of digitalisation in sustainability-oriented capacity development formats, in particular in hybrid settings that combine in-person and remotely connected learning partners. The work included inter alia a hybrid expert peer-exchange on training for local leadership and a two-day reflection and planning workshop with schools of public administrations and further training institutions.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Sophie
Last Name	Lampert
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Germany
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	11.02.2023
End date of secondment	16.04.2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	FGV EBAPE/ENAP
Email address	Sophielampert06@gmail.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting
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	<p>background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p> <p>Although we did end our final report with an extensive conclusion, we have not yet developed explicit recommendations, which will be taken up by myself and Sophia, who will stay at IDOS to work on the publication of our report. The subsequent publication of our results thus also depicts a future work package.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Secondment at Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), India
First Name	Anh Vy
Last Name	Dang
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	Vietnamese
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Early Stage Researcher (ESR)
Start date of secondment	19.07.2023
End date of secondment	17.08.2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS)
Email address	Vy.dang@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

India's G20 presidency has made Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) a central offering, showcasing its beneficial experience of technology and digitalisation and its relevance for countries of various income levels. Meanwhile, similar discussions are taking place in other

	<p>regions, notably within the European Union (EU). The EU has recently introduced Digital Commons as an innovative model for shared and collective governance over essential digital resources. Given the potential of DPI and Digital Commons in advancing sustainable development goals (SDGs), there is a pressing need to align these diverse perspectives, experiences, and debates. This synergy will contribute to the ongoing discussions surrounding the UN Global Digital Compact, planned to be agreed during the Summit of the Future in September 2024. However, a significant challenge in such synergy endeavour lies in terminological confusion of the key terms DPI and Digital Commons.</p> <p>Therefore, the main aim of the secondment is to unpack these terms and contrast international perspectives on these concepts. The goal is to align these diverse perspectives to advance sustainable development goals (SDGs) and contribute to the discussions surrounding the UN Global Digital Compact, planned for agreement during the Summit of the Future in September 2024. To achieve this, the secondment is structured in the following key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk research to collect information, current debates and publications and official statements on DPI and Digital Commons. This step aims to establish a foundational understanding of these concepts, their development, and the various perspectives surrounding them. • Exchanges with experts at host institute and other institutions within the Managing Global Governance (MGG) network in India to gain insights on how India prioritises DPI during its G20 Presidency. • Participating in the Think20 (T20) Summit to observe and gather input on the priorities of India on DPI. This provides first-hand exposure to the global discussions and initiatives related to DPI. • Co-organising a Side Event at the T20 Summit with the partner institute Gateway House: Indian Council on Global Relations on the topic “Utopias of Global Cooperation: Towards joint Visions of Global Digital Commons” to collect inputs and contrast international perspectives on this topic. It is an opportunity to facilitate a dialogue among experts and stakeholders from different world regions. <p>The secondment generated rich inputs, insights, and data on DPI and Digital Commons. These inputs serve as a foundation for the publication and research presentation at the end of the secondment, which can further disseminate the knowledge and contribute to a better understanding of these concepts.</p> <p>The project also suggests that this topic can be further developed in the future. This could involve investigating similar initiatives in other countries or world regions, or monitoring if and how discussions around DPI evolve in upcoming G20 presidencies.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Anh Vy
Last Name	Dang
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	Vietnamese
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	29 October 2024
End date of secondment	28 November 2024
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV)
Email address	Vy.Dang@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (*For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.*)

Building on the previous secondment in India in 2023, this secondment aims to explore and analyse Brazil's approach to digitalisation, particularly Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI), during its G20 presidency. By contrasting Brazil's G20 priorities with those of India, the research seeks to

	<p>understand the evolving international perspectives on DPI and the role of the G20 in shaping these discussions.</p> <p>To achieve this, the secondment is structured in the following key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk research to collect information on Brazil’s G20 priorities, current debates and publications and official statements on DPI. • Exchanges with experts at FGV and other experts within the Managing Global Governance Programme to gain insights on Brazil’s G20 presidency and its priorities (within a framework of an MGG national network meeting with Brazilian network members in Brasilia, Brazil) • Participated in the Think20 (T20) Summit to understand the G20-related processes and Brazil’s G20 priorities • Co-organised a Side Event at the T20 Summit with the partner organisation Institute of Applied Economic Research (IPEA) on the topic “Global cooperation on sustainable development after the 2024 election year” for a cross-country reflection of the conditions for international cooperation in the field of digitalisation, climate progressive taxation.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	PD Dr Dr
First Name	Ariel Macaspac
Last Name	Hernandez
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	2 May 2022
End date of secondment	31 May 2022
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability
Host institute	FGV EBAPE
Email address	Ariel.hernandez@idos-research.de
Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	<p>The main purpose of the trip was to gain contextual knowledge of the complexity of achieving food security through the reduction of food waste and loss in Brazil and to gain insights on how digitalization can help design and implement sustainability standards in the food sector. One major achievement of the trip is the partnership with INMETRO, which became more aware of the issues related to food waste and loss. The interviewed stakeholders were keen on partnering with INMETRO and also with the other stakeholders. Interestingly, the stakeholders do not have any space or platform to exchange experiences with each other. This is an opportunity for IDOS or INMETRO to pursue in the future.</p> <p>Another opportunity is to tap FGV to coordinate similar efforts of bringing together stakeholders, as it is doing in other cases such as in sustainability reporting.</p>

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Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Judith
Last Name	Böckle
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR/Admin
Start date of secondment	27.04.2022-
End date of secondment	27.05.2022
Originating institution	German Development Institute DIE
Host institute	Instituto Mora
Email address	Judith.boeckle@die-gdi.de
Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	Gaining knowledge and experience on the conceptualisation of hybrid formats for training and exchange on sustainable development to foster inclusive exchange and to create a participatory and interactive atmosphere among participants online as well as in presence.

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Anita
Last Name	Breuer
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Swiss / German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	16. February 2024
End date of secondment	16 March 2024
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	GV - Fundação Getulio Vargas
Email address	Anita.breuer@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	During my stay in Brazil, I conducted field research on the topic "Information Integrity and Pollution: enablers, drivers and impact on social cohesion and democracy in Brazil." I applied an analytical framework developed by UNDP to study information pollution. According to this framework, four contexts are considered particularly relevant: 1) political landscape, 2) media landscape, 3) social landscape, 4) legislative and institutional landscape. In order to learn more about the drivers and
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	<p>impacts of information pollution in these four contexts, during my stay I conducted semi-structured interviews with 32 experts. Experts included the following types of actors: media professionals, civil servants, academics (scholars of sociology as well as political and communication science), members of civil society organizations, and practitioners in international development cooperation. Furthermore, during my stay, in coordination with Prof. Gregory Michener (FGV EBAPE), I organized and conducted a webinar entitled <i>“To inform and to misinform: The current state of Brazil’s information eco-system”</i> that served both as additional instrument of data collection as well as an opportunity for academic exchanges. In accordance with the analytical framework of my research project, the webinar was structured into four individual sessions in which a Brazilian expert from each of the relevant context provided an input of 10 minutes, followed by an open discussion among all panellists. The webinar, which was held on 12. March 2024, was streamed live on the YouTube channel of FGV and is available there as a digital knowledge product.</p> <p>A second digital knowledge product is being elaborated jointly with FGV’s School of Communication, Media and Information (ECMI). On 14. March 2024 I gave a video interview about current global trends of autocratization, polarization and digital disinformation, providing first insights into my finding from Brazil. The interview will be edited by FGV ECMI and made available as a digital knowledge product in April 2024.</p> <p>The work still to be done includes the transcription of the audio recordings of the interviews I conducted, as well as their systematic analysis. On this basis, I will prepare a publication in the IDOS Discussion Paper series - , envisaged publication end of 2024.</p> <p>Furthermore, in cooperation with IDOS communication department (Sabrina Heuwinkel) I am currently working on the production of another digital knowledge product on the topic of “Combating disinformation beyond content regulation” and in which I will present video statements which I collected from representatives of several Brazilian digital initiatives during my research stay.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Anita
Last Name	Breuer
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Swiss / German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	9. January 2023
End date of secondment	7 February 2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	Instituto de Investigaciones Dr. José Maria Luis Mora
Email address	Anita.breuer@idos-research.de

Technical summary of work	<p>During my stay in Mexico, I conducted field research on the topic "<i>Information Integrity and Pollution: enablers, drivers and impact on social cohesion and democracy in Mexico.</i>" I applied an analytical framework developed by UNDP to study information pollution. According to this framework four contexts are considered particularly relevant: 1) political landscape, 2) media landscape, 3) social landscape, 4) legislative and institutional</p>
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	<p>landscape. In order to learn more about the drivers and impacts of information pollution in these four contexts, during my stay I conducted 16 semi-structured interviews with the following types of actors: media professionals, civil servants, academics (scholars of sociology as well as political and communication science), members of civil society organizations, and practitioners in international development cooperation. Furthermore, during my stay, I transcribed and systematized my handwritten interview notes and on this basis I prepared a Power-Point presentation that summarized my preliminary findings. I presented these during a hybrid discussion event jointly organized by IDOS, Instituto Mora and Visor Urbano on February 3, 2023. The event was recorded and is available as a digital knowledge product on the Internet. The work still to be done includes the transcription of the audio recordings of the interviews I conducted, as well as their systematic analysis. On this basis, I will prepare a discussion paper or policy brief, envisaged publication before end of 2023.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Eva
Last Name	Lynders
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	21 August 2022
End date of secondment	21 September 2022
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)
Email address	Eva.Lynders@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (*For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.*)

The research agenda was framed as “explorative”, combining desk research with meetings and expert talks to gather background knowledge on the field.

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Prof. Dr.
First Name	Francisco Javier
Last Name	Porras Sánchez
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	Mexican
Status – ESR or ER? (Early-Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	18 th July 2022
End date of secondment	15 th September 2022 (60 days)
Originating institution	Instituto Mora (Instituto de Investigaciones Dr. José María Luis Mora)
Host institute	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Email address	fporras@institutomora.edu.mx

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you

The objective of the secondment was to conduct research (including exchanges with the

<p><i>make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i></p>	<p>IDOS staff and interviews with relevant informants) in order to write the Discussion Paper (DP) <i>Digitalization and Governance for Sustainable Development in Mexico</i>.</p> <p>The DP proposed a hypothesis, and a resulting research agenda, on the role played by digitalization for sustainable development in Mexico, using insights and information from relevant actors coming from the governmental, academic, non-governmental, and the media sectors, both European and Mexican. The DP explored the main situated actors, beliefs, practices, traditions, dilemmas, and narratives related to digitalization processes to promote sustainable development in Mexico. It also elaborated on the role played by open data and how they are taken into account by relevant governmental and non-governmental actors.</p> <p>The complete draft was submitted on the 30th of November 2022. It is expected that observations and suggestions will be received once the DP is reviewed by IDOS, and that the correction process will continue at least for a couple of months.</p> <p>The DP research and writing process identified valuable contacts in Germany and established useful links for future collaboration projects.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Mara
Last Name	Braun
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	11.02.2023
End date of secondment	15.04.2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	FGV
Email address	Marasophiabraun@web.de

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting
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	<p>background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p> <p>Although we did end our final report with an extensive conclusion, we have not yet developed explicit recommendations, which will be taken up by XX, who will stay at IDOS to work on the publication of our report. The subsequent publication of our results thus also depicts a future work package.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Marcel
Last Name	Wich
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Early Stage Researcher
Start date of secondment	11 th of April 2023
End date of secondment	16 th of April 2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability
Host institute	FGV EBAPE
Email address	Marcel.wich@idos-research.de / m.wich@me.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	<p>Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different</p>
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	<p>administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p> <p>Although we did end our final report with an extensive conclusion, we have not yet developed explicit recommendations, which will be taken up by our colleagues, who will stay at IDOS to work on the publication of our report. The subsequent publication of our results thus also depicts a future work package.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Ms.
First Name	Irina
Last Name	Rafliana
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	
Nationality	Indonesia
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	PhD Researcher/Experienced Researcher with 16 years experiences.
Start date of secondment	4 February 2022
End date of secondment	5 June 2022
Originating institution	German Development Institute (DIE)
Host institute	CSIS Indonesia
Email address	irina.rafliana@die-gdi.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	The field work supported is an instrumental part of my doctoral thesis research titled: Traveling Waves of Knowledge and Technology: the Indonesian Tsunami Warning System. The field work expresses connectivity between German epistemic groups and technologies to reduce tsunami risks and Indonesian tsunami epistemic groups at the National Tsunami Warning Center (BMKG), at the Agency for Research and Innovation (BRIN) and 3 different sites and communities at tsunami risks in Indonesia.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	PhD Cand.
First Name	Noory
Last Name	Okthariza
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	Indonesia
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	September 21, 2022
End date of secondment	December 12, 2022
Originating institution	CSIS Indonesia
Host institute	LUISS Guido Carli
Email address	noory.okthariza@csis.or.id

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	I studied the policy-making process behind the issuance of the Indonesian Personal Data Protection Law. I conducted desk research at LUISS and interviewed a number of stakeholders during my secondment. I worked alongside Professor Thomas Christiansen and wrote and presented a paper on this topic at the
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Digital Transformation and Sustainability of Pharmaceutical Industry
First Name	Mario
Last Name	Miozza
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	Italian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	9/10/2023
End date of secondment	8/02/2024
Originating institution	Luiss University
Host institute	RIS
Email address	mmiozza@luiss.it

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	Produced a qualitative paper on the barriers and drivers for the Sustainability and Digital Transformation of the Pharmaceutical Industry based on 16 Interviews with practitioners; a quantitative paper on the relations between AI and SDG performance; a Systematic Literature
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Gustavo
Last Name	Sosa-Nunez
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Mexican
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	09.09.2020
End date of secondment	08.09.2020
Originating institution	Instituto Mora
Host institute	Hamburg University
Email address	gsosa@mora.edu.mx

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	The research project aims to examine the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in climate change mitigation and adaptation policies, making a comparative assessment between the European Union (EU), Germany and Mexico. In this sense, the focus of the work carried out during the secondment at Hamburg University was on
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	<p>retrieving as many and as varied information as possible in terms of theoretic and interdisciplinary academic research made on the topic, to deepen into the understanding and potential uses of AI. This approach has entailed considering environmental, climatic, social, anthropologic, technological, ethical, and policy perspectives about the type of research I am conducting.</p> <p>The understanding of the links between these perspectives implies a thorough assessment of the information I have retrieved during the secondment at Hamburg University, which I am currently doing. With this information, I am starting to write a document expecting to publish it throughout the year 2021.</p> <p>It is worth mentioning that my secondment was fully funded by the Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (DAAD), and I made no use of economic support from the EU-funded PRODIGEES project.</p> <p>Additionally, due to the current Covid-19 context, some of the interviews I held were virtual. In a couple of cases, interviewees did not sign data consent and informed consent forms. In some other cases, date of signature differs from the date of interview, as interviewees sent their forms days afterwards.</p> <p>Taking into account the pandemic and that I had to interview some academics via digital means, I believe that my secondment was fruitful because I had access to them while being at UHH. Besides, it was extremely useful to have access to the UHH digital database, which has a wider reach and scope than that of the home institution.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Carlos
Last Name	Domínguez
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	MEXICAN
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Experienced researcher
Start date of secondment	September 18 th September
End date of secondment	November 17 th November
Originating institution	Instituto Mora
Host institute	DIE-BONN
Email address	alcarlosv@gmail.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	I used the time to conduct interviews, complete literature review on digitalisation and inequalities, and discussed it with colleagues from different institutions in Germany
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Manfredi
Last Name	Valeriani
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Italian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	28/01/2024
End date of secondment	27/03/2024
Originating institution	Luiss Guido Carli
Host institute	Stellenbosch University
Email address	mvaleriani@luiss.it

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	The early idea was to investigate innovation and participatory initiatives at the urban level in the city of cape town. An early review of the initiatives showed a predomination of initiatives related to urban agriculture and community building. The research has then moved in understanding how these initiatives fit within the broader local food systems and how they produce social capital. While a series of initiatives have been mapped
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	during the period in South Africa, contacts and interviews are still undergoing, possibly planning a second period in South Africa.
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PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Sabrina
Last Name	Heuwinkel
Gender	female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Experienced Communication expert
Start date of secondment	26.09.2023
End date of secondment	29.10.2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	FGV EBAPE
Email address	Sabrina.heuwinkel@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	During the secondment stay, I took part in the "Amazon immersion experience" excursion offered by FGV EBAPE. The excursion offers Brazilian and international students insights into the topic of sustainability and is a course in the Master in Management (MIM). The excursion gave me the opportunity to learn
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	<p>about environmental projects and sustainable management practices implemented by different public and private sector actors in the Amazon region. The aim of my stay was to produce knowledge products as part of a science communications project to demonstrate how positive solutions and practical approaches can be demonstrated in a very concrete way through interviews and videos. During my stay I was able to edit and finish one video for our partner about the expedition. The video (7 minutes lengths) portrays the expedition and portrays local entrepreneurs in the Amazon region.</p> <p>https://youtu.be/rLd7nswLoM0</p> <p>I also produced 6 interviews, which needs to be translated from Portuguese into English and then will be edited as well. Once the production process is finished all videos on digitalisation and sustainability will be published on social media and YouTube.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Secondment at Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), India
First Name	Eva-Maria
Last Name	Lynders
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Early Stage Researcher (ESR)
Start date of secondment	19.07.2023
End date of secondment	17.08.2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS),
Email address	Eva.Lynders@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

The secondment structured in the following key activities:

- Organisation of Managing Global Governance (MGG) Network Meeting with Indian network members on India's priorities in the G20

	<p>process and exchange of experiences in G20 processes amongst network members.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participating in the Think20 (T20) Summit and prepare background talks on cooperation patterns within the T20 policy community• Co-organising a Side Event at the T20 Summit with the partner institute Gateway House: Indian Council on Global Relations on the topic “Utopias of Global Cooperation: Towards joint Visions of Global Digital Commons” to collect inputs and contrast international perspectives on this topic as an opportunity for dialogue among experts and stakeholders from different world regions.
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Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Eva
Last Name	Lynders
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	29 October 2024
End date of secondment	28 November 2024
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV)
Email address	Eva.Lynders@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (*For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.*)

The aim of this research stay has been to analyse the outcomes of the Think20 (T20) Brazil process as well as the conditions for global cooperation after the election year of 2024. A special focus was put on cooperation on AI and digitalisation, as reflected in T20 Task Force 05 “Inclusive Digital

	Transformation” as well as on the intersections of digitalisation and climate policies and the role of AI in political polarisation processes.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Laura
Last Name	Fichtner
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	March 31 st , 2023
End date of secondment	April 28 th , 2023
Originating institution	University of Hamburg
Host institute	Fundação Getulio Vargas
Email address	Laura.fichtner@uni-hamburg.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	Comparative research on Brazilian platform regulation & governance – investigating the function of national platform regulation as a tool of democratic platform governance
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Sven
Last Name	Grimm
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment, first leg	11.02.2023 to 04.03.2023
End date of secondment, second leg	01.04.2023 to 15.04.2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	FGV, Brazil
Email address	sven.grimm@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

Our research investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil as well as governance mechanisms for digitalisation and their considerations.
We applied mixed methods, using both

	<p>qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting interviews and background conversations with experts in the field, as well as focus group discussions with civil servants as qualitative methods, complemented with a survey (quantitative method), we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts of digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants.</p> <p>Two participatory workshops were held in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. The report was published as an IDOS discussion paper in December 2024, providing a thoroughly investigated publication on the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Prof.
First Name	Janis
Last Name	Van der Westhuizen
Gender	M
Date of Birth	
Nationality	South African
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	5 June 2023
End date of secondment	4 July 2023
Originating institution	Stellenbosch University
Host institute	LUISS (Rome)
Email address	Jvdw2@sun.ac.za

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	Much of my time was spent doing both desktop research as well as face to face interviews. I was able to develop a basic outline of a research paper and presented this to my hosts. I obtained useful feedback and now need to incorporate this feedback into a more focussed paper.
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Matthias
Last Name	Kachelmann
Gender	male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	17.02.2025
End date of secondment	25.03.2025
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Host institute	Instituto Mora, Mexico City (Mexico)
Email address	Matthias.Kachelmann@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

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Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Leanne
Last Name	Seeliger
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	South African
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	23 November 2025
End date of secondment	23 December 2025
Originating institution	Stellenbosch University
Host institute	IDOS
Email address	seeliger@sun.ac.za

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

I was trying to work out whether digitalisation could help local government to improve their management of water resources. I made considerable progress in ascertaining this by completing a 3 year research project where digitalisation was used by citizens to monitor water pollution. The conclusion following my

	<p>discussions at IDOS with colleagues was that digitilisation is not a magic wand but that it requires institutional commitments to transforming management systems as well as levels of social cohesion in communities that can be difficult to achieve.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Sophia
Last Name	Hörbelt
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Early Stage Researcher
Start date of secondment	11 th of April 2023
End date of secondment	16 th of April 2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability
Host institute	FGV EBAPE
Email address	Sophia.Hoerbelt@idos-research.de / Sophia.hoerbelt@gmail.com

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding
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	<p>of the ways in which civil servants at different administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p> <p>Although we did end our final report with an extensive conclusion, we have not yet developed explicit recommendations, which will be taken up by our colleagues, who will stay at IDOS to work on the publication of our report. The subsequent publication of our results thus also depicts a future work package.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Benjamin
Last Name	Stewart
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	American (USA)
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	03 Sep 2021
End date of secondment	18 Nov 2021
Originating institution	DIE
Host institute	MORA
Email address	Benjamin.stewart@die-gdi.de

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	I conducted numerous interviews on the topic of Open Science and digitalisation in order to perform a discourse analysis on Open Science as it pertains to digitalisation's role in a global common good. Participant observation and daily field notes, including observation of the premises of the host institute were essential to
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	<p>the research goal. Further interviews and observations need to be conducted at other PRODIGEES institutes in order to complete the comparative commentary on digitalisation and Open Science. This is in the context of WP2 on Governance and Society. Who has power of knowledge access, who is a part of which knowledge communities, which knowledge is accessible to whom and how (via what mediums) is crucial to understanding on what bases societies accept and reject knowledge, which knowledge is deemed credible (by policymakers, academics and the general public), and how to govern a plurality of epistemic communities with varying degrees of access to knowledge. Importantly, this study is an observation of and commentary on how digitalisation affects the governance of knowledge exchange, as a force for both simplifying and complexifying knowledge exchange.</p>
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Secondment Report & Activity Log

Title	Prof. Dr.
First Name	Ingrid
Last Name	Schneider
Gender	female
Date of Birth	
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	27.01.2020
End date of secondment	Planned: 26.03.2020 – real: 23.03.2020 due to Covid-19
Originating institution	UHAM – Universität Hamburg
Host institute	MORA – Instituto Mora
Email address	Ingrid.Schneider@uni-hamburg.de
Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	Gaining comparative knowledge of the Mexican reception and interpretation of the EU's regulation, in particular of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and anti-trust policies of GAFAM

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Prof. Dr.
First Name	Ingrid
Last Name	Schneider
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	16.01.22
End date of secondment	14.04.22
Originating institution	UHAM – University of Hamburg, Germany
Host institute	FGV-EBAPE, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Email address	Ingrid.Schneider@uni-hamburg.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	For my research on Digital Governance in Brazil, I conducted interviews on Digital Platform Regulation, Data Protection, Competition & AI Policy, Digital Rights, e-financial inclusion, Brazil's digital transformation, and gained important insights
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	<p>in whether the EU is a model of reference. Citizens' awareness of opportunities and risks in the digital realm was also part of my research project.</p> <p>Progress was made in comparative research on digital governance. Research results have been presented in Workshops, Seminars and conferences at host and home institution, and in Bonn and Vienna institutions, Publications are under preparation.</p>
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PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Prof.Dr.
First Name	Ingrid
Last Name	Schneider
Gender	female
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	07.01.2024
End date of secondment	04.04.2024 plus 24.-27.04.2024 = 92 days
Originating institution	Universität Hamburg
Host institute	Stellenbosch University
Email address	Ingrid.Schneider@uni-hamburg.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	My research objective was to gain comparative knowledge of data protection legislation, competition policies and artificial intelligence regulation vis-à-vis large digital platforms in South Africa. The measures taken were compared to those of the European Union. I also inquired whether the “Brussels effect” exists – both on paper, in
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	<p>legislative actions, and in practice. I reached these goals, as knowledge and insights could be gained via interviews, official documents, and literature research. Publication of research results still needs to be carried out.</p>
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Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

Secondment Report & Activity Log

First name	Ingrid		Surname	Schneider
Date of birth		Gender	female	ER (with doctoral degree / 4 years FT equivalent research experience) or ESR (within first 4 years of research career)
Originating Institution	UHAM		Host Institution	CSIS
Start date of Secondment <i>(counted from the time of leaving home)</i>	08.01.2025		End date of Secondment <i>(the date of arrival back in home country)</i>	06.02.2025
Researcher's email address	Ingrid.Schneider@uni-hamburg.de			
Address of residence on secondment	Menteng Park Apartments, Emerald Tower, 35B. Jl. Cikini Raya No.79, RT.2/RW.2, Cikini, Kec. Menteng, Kota Jakarta Pusat, Daerah Khusus Ibukota Jakarta 10330			
Nationality	German			

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Secondment Report & Activity Log

First name	Prof. Dr. Ingrid		Surname	Schneider
Date of birth [REDACTED]		Gender female	ER (with doctoral degree / 4 years FT equivalent research experience) or ESR (within first 4 years of research career)	ER
Originating Institution	UHAM		Host Institution	RIS
Start date of Secondment (counted from the time of leaving home)	09.01.2023		End date of Secondment (the date of arrival back in home country)	08.04.2023
Researcher's email address	Ingrid.Schneider@uni-hamburg.de			
Address of residence on secondment	70, Amrit Nagar, Part I, New Delhi, 110003 India			
Nationality	Germany			

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

How to use this activity log: Please use this form to record your activities, meetings summaries, flight dates etc. that are relevant to your secondment. Please include dates, locations, and events. Scanned images or photos of boarding passes can be inserted into this log file. When in doubt, err on the side of more detail rather than less. The point of this log is to prove that seconded staff devoted full-time to the PRODIGEES action during the secondment period, and to show that the researcher was on-the-ground performing work relevant to PRODIGEES. Please forward this log file with the requisite signatures to the PRODIGEES Project Manager (Benjamin Stewart: benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de) and CC the host supervisor and your home institution's PRODIGEES Steering Committee Member.

Secondment Activity Report

Title	Mr.
First Name	Benjamin
Last Name	Stewart
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	USA
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	January 9, 2023
End date of secondment	March 16, 2023
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	CSIS
Email address	Benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (<i>For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.</i>)	This research investigates the implementation of Open Science policies in Indonesia in the context of digitalisation. The key focus is on understanding the implementation of science and technology policies in Indonesia's scientific ecosystem. In parallel, the research investigates Indonesia's position in Southeast
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	<p>Asia and the Asia-Pacific region, in the context of science and technology policy. Qualitative methodologies are used to conduct the research of this study. Interviews are conducted with key institutions of the Indonesian science ecosystem, including the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), research institutes, universities, and civil society organisations.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Benjamin
Last Name	Stewart
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 20px;"></div>
Nationality	USA
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	12 April 2024
End date of secondment	11 May 2024
Originating institution	IDOS
Host institute	Stellenbosch Universityb
Email address	Benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	My PRODIGEES work is an investigation of Open Science implementation in the South African context. This includes engagement with policy training in digitalisation and capacity building with training and learning, also in the context of digitalisation. These elements connect with the science
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	<p>communication and public good components of Open Science. A key secondment objective is to establish strong network connections to key actors in Open Science in South Africa in order to obtain points of comparison for implementation of Open Science in reference to the global framework from UNESCO.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Matthias
Last Name	Kachelmann
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<input type="text"/>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	17.02.2025
End date of secondment	25.03.2025
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	Instituto Mora (MORA), CDMX, Mexico
Email address	matthias.kachelmann@idos-research.de

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Wulf
Last Name	Reiners
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<input type="text"/>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	17.02.2025
End date of secondment	25.03.2025
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	Instituto Mora (MORA), CDMX, Mexico
Email address	wulf.reiners@idos-research.de

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Benjamin
Last Name	Stewart
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<input type="text"/>
Nationality	USA
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	17.02.2025
End date of secondment	25.03.2025
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	Instituto Mora (MORA), CDMX, Mexico
Email address	benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de

PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Mr.
First Name	Alif
Last Name	Satria
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Indonesian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	September 16 th , 2022
End date of secondment	December 12 th , 2022
Originating institution	Centre for Strategic and International Studies, Indonesia
Host institute	LUISS
Email address	isalifsatria@ntu.edu.sg

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Sven
Last Name	Grimm
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment, first leg	21.04.2024 to 07.05.2024
End date of secondment, second leg	13.10. to 27.10.2024
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	Stellenbosch University, South Africa
Email address	sven.grimm@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work (For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)

The policy labs serve as collaborative forums, in which an international group of participants engage in a dynamic working model that merges insights from PRODIGEES R&I endeavours since 2020. The objective was to formulate

	<p>recommendations for policy-makers at the intersection of digitalisation and sustainable development in specialized focus areas across governance and society, and economy and environment. Beyond the formulation of policy advice, the meeting also served the purpose to develop the future PRODIGEES agenda, network with local institutions, and explore digitalisation experiences in the South African context. Results were presented and discussed in various ensuing formats, including an international conference of MGG/IDOS and the National School of Government (NSG) in Cape Town on May 4-9, 2024.</p> <p>The second leg of the secondment followed the rationale of policy relevance in connecting with policy relevant institutions (Policy Innovation Lab, Stellenbosch, and SAIIA, Johannesburg), while also presenting work to students and discussing with colleagues at Stellenbosch University.</p>
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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Mr
First Name	Beltsazar
Last Name	Krisetya
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Indonesian
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	Early-Stage Researchers
Start date of secondment	17 May 2023
End date of secondment	13 August 2023
Originating institution	Centre for Strategic and International Studies, Jakarta
Host institute	Universität Hamburg
Email address	b.krisetya@csis.or.id

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	My secondment at Universität Hamburg (May–August 2023), supported by the EU-funded PRODIGEES programme, explored whether Indonesia should adopt the European Union's Digital Services Act (DSA) to improve its content moderation policies. The research found that while the DSA offers valuable principles—such as transparency, independent oversight, and risk-based obligations—Indonesia's centralised governance structure and lack of institutional safeguards make direct
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	<p>adoption unfeasible. Through comparative legal analysis and expert interviews across Europe and Indonesia, the study highlighted the need for a tailored regulatory model suited to Indonesia's political and legal context. The findings now inform ongoing work at the Safer Internet Lab (SAIL), laying the groundwork for further inquiry into adaptive regulatory design, the impact of content governance on digital rights, and the global diffusion of EU digital norms.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	
First Name	Citlali
Last Name	Ayala Martinez
Gender	F
Date of Birth	[REDACTED]
Nationality	Mexican
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	May 28
End date of secondment	June 28
Originating institution	Instituto Mora
Host institute	IDOS
Email address	cayala@institutomora.edu.mx

Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i>	The stay at IDOS consisted of continuing the research on the role of digitalisation in South-South cooperation. Interviews were conducted with United Nations officials in Bonn, as well as with the German cooperation agency GIZ and the Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ). I carried out and desk
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	<p>research on some case studies to ground the research in what offered more evidence on cooperation alliances between non-governmental actors for the use of digital inputs in development solutions.</p> <p>The progress in the research was substantial because with the desk research and the interviews it was possible to obtain an analysis based on the variables of digitalisation, sustainable development and South-South cooperation at IDOS, BMZ and the United Nations. The findings derived in the article show the conjunction between the guidelines suggested by the global digital pact, the trends of South-South cooperation and the practices in the use of drones for development in Africa and their replicability in regions with similar problems. The research allows me to look for similar cases in Central and Latin America.</p>
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PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Wulf
Last Name	Reiners
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<input type="text"/>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	12.04.2024
End date of secondment	11.05.2024
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	University of Stellenbosch, South Africa
Email address	wulf.reiners@idos-research.de

Provide a technical summary of work *(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)*

The main aim of the secondment is to identify and address key potentials and challenges of digitalisation policies for sustainable development – particularly in areas like poverty, inequality and unemployment. By integrating partner institutions in South Africa, notably the University of Stellenbosch and The National School of Government, we aim to harness and synergize existing expertise on capacity development (specifically in the training of civil servants) and drafting impactful policy advice.

To achieve this, the secondment is structured alongside the following key activities:

- Desk research to collect information, current debates, news, and publications
- Exchanges with experts at the host institute (University of Stellenbosch) and other institutions within the Managing Global Governance (MGG), particularly The National School of Government, in South Africa
- Co-organising and participating in the “MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs - Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development” in Stellenbosch and “the NSG-IDOS Conference on “International Capacity Development for the Civil Service – The Sustainable Digitalisation Agenda” in Cape Town

PRODIGEES

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr
First Name	Wulf
Last Name	Reiners
Gender	Male
Date of Birth	<input type="text"/>
Nationality	German
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ER
Start date of secondment	11.02.2023
End date of secondment	15.04.2023
Originating institution	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Germany
Host institute	FGV, Brazil
Email address	wulf.reiners@idos-research.de

<p>Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i></p>	<p>Within our research, we investigated the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. Therefore, we applied mixed methods, using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to obtain an in-depth understanding of the ways in which civil servants at different administrative levels make sense of digitalisation and its application for sustainability-related purposes. By conducting background conversations with experts in the field, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with civil servants as well as a survey, we obtained a profound understanding of the ways in which the concepts digitalisation, sustainability, and their interconnection are perceived amongst civil servants. Additionally, we held two participatory workshops in Brazil to ensure our research is properly adjusted to the country context and to receive feedback from an experienced sounding board. Our findings were captured in our final report, sent out to the staff at IDOS and thereafter presented in our final presentation on May 25th. Hence, we did succeed in thoroughly investigating the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability amongst civil servants in Brazil.</p>
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PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

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Secondment Activity Report

Title	Dr.
First Name	Miriam
Last Name	Ordoñez Balanzario
Gender	Female
Date of Birth	<div style="background-color: black; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div>
Nationality	Mexican
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researchers are researchers without a PhD and with less than 4 years of experience. An Experienced Researcher is a researcher with a PhD and more than 4 years of research experience. Please consult the Grant Agreement for more details.)	ESR
Start date of secondment	September 20, 2022
End date of secondment	November 26, 2022
Originating institution	Instituto Mora
Host institute	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)
Email address	mordonez@institutomora.edu.mx

<p>Provide a technical summary of work <i>(For example what were you trying to achieve, what progress did you make, what further work needs to be carried out? Consider the work package tasks assigned to you.)</i></p>	<p>The objectives of the secondment can be summarized in two aspects: Objective 1.- to support the re-conceptualization of the Global Governance Academy in the framework of the implementation of the 2022 edition and Objective 2.- to contribute to joint research on the nexus between sustainability and digitalisation.</p> <p>The report gives an account of the activities carried out during the secondment period and the products produced so far, but some milestones are highlighted below:</p> <p>Objective 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I contributed to the strengthening of the coaching strategy of the participants in the Change Maker Projects design process. - I facilitated the implementation of the CMP by the company with which my team worked. - I strengthened the team's group work. - I contributed to identify areas of opportunity for the design of the next edition of the MGG. <p>Objective 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of a strategy through core questions to analyze the nexus between sustainability and digitalisation. - Exploration of the topic based on evidence derived from interviews with specialists. - Systematization of the meetings with specialists and production of a video, an article and two dissemination events. -key factors identified around the nexus between the two concepts which are relevant to the design of training formats for civil servants <p>The following steps are defined in the Future Action Plan (see Appendix 1) and are based on the core questions strategy mentioned above.</p>
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